

SMALL IS BEAUTIFUL: INVESTMENTS IN SYSTEMATIC INVESTMENT PLAN, ITS ASSOCIATION WITH RISK INVOLVED AND INVESTMENT OBJECTIVES OF A MUTUAL FUND INVESTOR

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ABSTRACT

In the development of a country's economy the role of financial market is significant in nature. In order the economy to prosper, strong financial system is a critical. Convert the savings of an individual into productive investments is one of the important functions of the financial market. Indian mutual fund industry has a key role in the capital formation of a country. Mutual funds provide an opportunity to investors to invest in a diversified and liquid portfolio. In the current study researcher aimed at understanding the investment objectives of an investor in mutual fund along with identifying the level of awareness of the risks associated with SIP and mutual fund investment. Researcher adopted various statistical tools to determine the significant impact of investment objectives and awareness of risks associated with investment in mutual funds.

Keywords: Mutual funds, SIP, Investments, Risk, Financial Markets, savings and capital formation.

I. Introduction

The accumulation of capital plays a very important role in a nation's economic development. The accumulation of capital is the method of adding capital to the stock per annum. The formation of capital increases a country's savings and investment. Thus, savings are one of the key elements in the development of capital and it should be seen as a part of discretionary income. Savings are used as investment to generate future revenues.

Most investors lack sufficient understanding of financial markets and its operational aspects. So they need specialist assistance to invest their hard-earned money in the appropriate financial instrument. There are humongous alternatives for the investors to invest. Some are at high risk and others are at low risk. Choosing the best investment from the

plenty of investment options is considered to be the most complex behavior.

II. Review of Literature

Chitra (2015) the relationship of behavioral factors such as allusion, remorse, hesitation, confidence, self-reliance, risk aversion, rational choice and constructive to scientific, fundamental and consumer psychology was proved in her paper.

Mohd IM Alnajjar (2013) examined the investor's irrational behavior when investing in the stock market and developed the model of psychological decision-making. The data proved investor acts irrationally in most situations.

Vaibhav Jain (2012) Studied different theoretical frameworks, such as over and under reaction, mental compartments, overconfidence, restricting disjunction results to arbitration, prospects and anticipated theories of utility.

Shun-Yao Tseng (2012) examined how the search aspect of information affects

VI. Research Methodology

a. **Research Design:** The study is conceived as

individual investment preferences such as stock / options investment and mutual fund investment. Heuristics had a favorable impact on expectations for investing in mutual funds. The quest for information affects investment preferences.

descriptive, based on primary and secondary data.

III. Research Gap

In this context, concerns from the viewpoint of individual investors and intermediaries of mutual funds have been posed following research questions. The research has been conducted to address the following questions:

b. **Source of Data:** The secondary as well as primary data were collected and used for study

- What are the investment objectives of mutual fund investors and their rationales to invest in the mutual fund?
- Whether and to which degree the investors are aware of Systemic Investment Plan?

(a) **Primary Data:** Primary data has been collected from the mutual fund's investors using Systematic Investment Plan and Mutual Fund intermediaries. The primary data were collected using structured questionnaires and interview schedules.

(b) **Secondary Data:** Secondary data is obtained from newspapers, books, journals, publications of different mutual fund organizations, AMFI website, SEBI website, RBI website and Asset Management Companies websites.

IV. Objectives of the study

- To explore the investor's objectives of investment in mutual fund and their overall disposition toward mutual fund.
- To determine the awareness of risks associated with SIP and the level of preference of investors towards mutual fund investment.

c. Sampling Design

Multi-stage sampling was used for the collection of primary data. In the first stage, the 13 districts in the state of Andhra Pradesh was divided into three regions namely Rayalaseema region, Coastal region and northern coastal region. Data Analysis

V. Research Hypotheses

- There is no significant difference in investor's objectives of investment in mutual fund with their demographic profile.
- There is no significant difference in the awareness of risks associated with SIP and the level of preference of investors.

d. Investor's Investment Objective

The overall objectives of investors investment in mutual fund was grouped into six categories, namely construction of house, children's higher education, future contingencies, corpus fund for retirement, tax savings and purchase of an asset.

H₀: There is no significant difference in the investment objectives of mutual fund investors and their demographic profiles.

Table 1 Investor's investment objectives in mutual fund

Investment Objectives	Mean Score	Std. Deviation	Rank
construction of house	4.3111	1.74451	1

future contingencies	4.2511	1.34365	2
children's higher education	3.6911	1.55527	3
purchase of an asset	3.0422	1.72638	4
corpus fund for retirement	2.9533	1.37915	5
Tax savings	2.7511	1.74813	6

Source: compiled by researcher (Primary data)

The table 1 reveals that the investor's important objective of the investment in mutual fund is for constructing a house with a mean score of 4.31, followed by future contingencies with a mean value of (4.25), Children's higher education and purchase of an asset ranked as the third and fourth objectives with mean scores of 3.69 and 3.04 respectively.

Table 2 ANOVA-Investment objectives with demographic profiles

Investment Objectives v/s Demographic Variables	F value (p-value)					
	Construction of House	Children's Higher Education	Future Contingencies	Corpus Fund for Retirement	Tax Savings	Purchase of an Asset
Region	3.122 (.045)	4.015 (.019)	6.690 (.001)	1.704 (.183)	1.931 (.146)	.764 (.466)
Gender	2.726 (.099)	.889 (.346)	.159 (.691)	.315 (.575)	17.888 (.000)	.487 (.486)
Age Category	19.847 (.000)	28.211 (.000)	34.524 (.000)	9.238 (.099)	9.238 (.000)	22.602 (.000)
Educational Qualification	3.673 (.006)	3.196 (.013)	5.704 (.000)	8.208 (.000)	12.315 (.000)	8.941 (.000)
Monthly income	14.622 (.000)	5.300 (.000)	3.694 (.006)	14.834 (.000)	5.943 (.000)	1.799 (.128)
Occupation	20.660 (.000)	11.104 (.000)	8.910 (.000)	1.938 (.073)	29.637 (.000)	12.877 (.000)

Significant at 0.05 levels

Source: Compiled by researcher

The above table 2 reveals that there is no significant difference among region and investment objectives in three cases and significant in three investment objectives such

as construction of house, children's higher education and for future contingencies.

e. Awareness of Risks associated

In the current study, researcher attempted to understand the investors' awareness about various risk associated with mutual fund

investment. Mean scores were calculated for the various risk involved in mutual fund investment and tabulated in table 3.

Table 3 Investor's Awareness towards risks associated with investment in mutual funds and systematic investment plan

Risk	Mean	Std. Deviation	Rank
Market Risk	3.6178	.70039	1
Investment Risk	3.3889	.86112	2
Changes in Government Policy	3.2467	.89991	3
Liquidity Risk	2.7489	1.08423	4
Interest Rate Risk	2.5333	.97462	5
Credit Risk	2.3183	.96283	6
Inflation Risk	2.1038	.95535	7
Total Awareness Score=2.92			

Source: Survey data

From the above table 3 it is evident that, the investors agreed that the awareness of risk in a mutual fund in the order of market risk, investment risk, change in government policy, liquidity risk, interest rate risk, credit risk and inflation risk with mean scores of 3.62, 3.89, 3.25, 2.75, 2.53, 2.32 and 2.10 respectively.

Table 4 Association of level of awareness of risk involved in mutual fund investment and type of investor

Risk	Type of Investor						F value	P value
	Low risk		Medium risk		High risk			
	Mean score	SD	Mean score	SD	Mean score	SD		
Liquidity risk	2.693	.7891	2.789	.9112	2.763	.8382	6.81	.001
Market risk	3.265	.8910	3.491	.6410	4.065	.4532	14.70	.000
Inflation risk	2.065	.8388	2.142	1.031	2.178	1.10109	8.040	.000
Interest rate risk	2.3823	.96026	2.4980	.80792	2.7368	.58329	26.006	.000
Investment risk	3.1412	.76146	3.4000	.69282	3.6404	.74255	17.455	.000
Credit risk	2.2281	.96355	2.3254	1.16164	2.4286	1.06934	7.249	.001
Change in Govt policy	3.2552	.66117	3.2224	.76207	3.2712	.50437	6.654	.001

** Significant at 0.05 level

Source: compiled by researcher

The table 4 indicates that the investors have a low level of preference towards the mutual fund, they are more aware of the market risk and change in government policy with mean scores of 3.265 and 3.2552 and followed by the investment risk with mean score 3.1412.

VII. Findings and Conclusion

It is identified from the study that, the investor's important investment objective is constructing a house followed by for future contingencies. Study also revealed that the respondents from northern coastal andhra region weigh more importance to meet future contingencies whereas investors from coastal andhra and rayalaseema region prefer construction of house. The study highlights that, Investors awareness towards Systematic Investment Plan is comparatively low. Their awareness towards various risks is very low and most of the respondents have the moderate risk-bearing capacity.

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